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Detection, Identification and Characterization of CMV Proteins Able to Induce a Strong Immune Response Using Serum Samples from Patients that Have Developed a Protective Response Against CMV Infection.

Detección, Identificación y Caracterización de proteínas de CMV capaces de inducir una fuerte respuesta inmunológica empleando muestras de suero de pacientes que han desarrollado una respuesta protectora frente a la infección por CMV.

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ANEXO 3

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CERTIFICAN:

Que el trabajo titulado: **“Detection, Identification and Characterization of CMV Proteins Able to Induce a Strong Immune Response Using Serum Samples from Patients that Have Developed a Protective Response Against CMV Infection”**, ha sido realizado bajo mi dirección por el alumno/a D./D^a Jaanam Lalchandani Lakhani.

Alcalá de Henares, a 21 de octubre de 2020

Firmado:

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After 4 years apart from home during my BSc degree, it has been another year, another adventure in a completely unknown city for me. Now, at this moment in my life, I can't find words enough to say thank you for all that has happened to me during these five years. Of course, I give thanks even for those not so good, which helped me learn many more things in life.

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ABSTRACT

Due to the severity of CMV infection and the deaths associated to this pathogen, numerous attempts have been made to develop vaccines against CMV, however, the complex interaction between CMV and the immune system have hindered the development of a vaccine.

The aim of this study was to identify and characterize CMV antigens that induce an antibody immune response and could be used for vaccine design.

Serum samples from 29 kidney transplant recipients that exhibit both a high neutralizing antibody response and CMV-specific immune response were used as primary antibody. We detected by western blot antigens that were specifically recognized by the post-immunization serum compared with the baseline serum. Excised proteins were characterized and identified using LC-MS/MS. The open reading frames of the identified proteins were cloned, expressed in HEK 293-T cells and further detected by western blot using serum samples from immunized patients as primary antibodies.

Of the fourteen bands analysed, we were able to identify twelve different CMV proteins with molecular weight ranging from 30 to 280 kDa. Some of these proteins such as UL83 (pp65) and UL55 (gB) have previously shown to elicit a potent antibody response. In addition, we also identified other 10 CMV proteins that induce an antibody response in patients that have developed a protective CMV-specific response.

Using serum of immunized patients is an excellent strategy to identify CMV proteins that are able to stimulate an antibody-mediated immunity and may also be involved in mediating a cellular response. Analysis using these candidates for vaccine design will be further investigated.

KEYWORDS: Human cytomegalovirus, Immune response, Neutralizing antibodies, Solid organ transplant patients, HCMV Vaccines.

RESUMEN

Debido a la gravedad de la infección por citomegalovirus y las muertes asociadas a este patógeno, se han realizado numerosos intentos para desarrollar una vacuna, sin embargo, la compleja interacción entre CMV y el sistema inmunológico ha obstaculizado el desarrollo de esta.

El objetivo de este estudio fue identificar y caracterizar antígenos de CMV capaces de inducir una respuesta inmunológica mediada por anticuerpos que podrían emplearse para desarrollar vacunas.

Se empleó como anticuerpo primario suero de 29 receptores de trasplante de riñón que presentan una respuesta inmune específica a CMV, así como mediada por anticuerpos neutralizantes. Se detectaron antígenos que fueron reconocidos específicamente por el suero post-inmunización en comparación con el suero basal. Las proteínas extraídas se caracterizaron e identificaron mediante LC-MS/MS. Las pautas abiertas de lectura de las proteínas identificadas se clonaron y expresaron en células HEK 293-T y se detectaron posteriormente por western blot.

De las catorce bandas analizadas, pudimos identificar doce proteínas diferentes de CMV con pesos moleculares de 30 a 280 kDa. Algunas de estas proteínas como UL83 (pp65) y UL55 (gB) han demostrado previamente que generan una potente respuesta mediada por anticuerpos. Sin embargo, también identificamos otras 10 proteínas de CMV que inducen una respuesta de anticuerpos en pacientes que han desarrollado una respuesta protectora específica de CMV.

El uso de suero de pacientes inmunizados es una excelente estrategia para identificar proteínas virales capaces de estimular una inmunidad mediada por anticuerpos y que también pueden estar involucradas en la mediación de una respuesta celular.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Citomegalovirus humano, Respuesta inmune, Anticuerpos neutralizantes, Trasplante de órgano sólido, Vacunas.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Characteristics of cytomegalovirus (CMV)

1.1.1. *Herpesviridae* family

Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV or HHV-5) belongs to the *Herpesviridae* family, *Betaherpesviridae* subfamily. The *Herpesviridae* family presents several common characteristics in terms of structure and genome. Cytomegalovirus has a double-stranded linear DNA genome surrounded by a nucleocapsid, and a protein based tegument and all encompassed by a double lipid membrane composed of both: viral and host proteins¹.

Herpesviruses have two replication phases: a lytic phase, in which viral replication leads to lysis of the host cell, and a latent phase, during which they are able to establish lifelong infections through the insertion of the viral DNA into the infected cell genome and the evasion of the immune system. Cytomegalovirus has a slow reproductive cycle and establish latency in leukocytes or white blood cells².

1.1.2. Genome and Structure

Cytomegalovirus is the largest virus able to infect humans¹ with a large genome of 235 Kbp, with approximately 192 Open Reading Frames (ORFs) encoding for potential proteins. The ORFs encodes about 165 genes and has a single origin of replication¹. The genome consists of a unique long (UL) and a unique short (US) domain flanked by terminal repeated sequences (TRL and TRS) and by internal repeats (IRL and IRS)³. Genes are classified according to their expression: Immediate Early (IE or α), Early (E or β) and Late (L or γ) expression genes, which are further divided into two categories: "leaky-late genes", which are independent of DNA synthesis, and "true-late genes", which are dependent on DNA synthesis⁴.

The structure of CMV is divided into three main regions: An icosahedral nucleocapsid presenting a linear double-stranded DNA genome of the virus. The CMV nucleocapsid presents 162 capsomers and consists entirely of viral proteins, which together account for 30% of total virion proteins. A protein tegument surrounding the capsid composed of 14 different proteins. They have multiple functions, participating in virus entry into the host cell, expression of viral genes, evasion of the immune system, assembly and exit of new viral progeny. The most prominent tegument protein is the 65 kDa phosphoprotein (pp65 or UL83), that is highly antigenic, hence it is used as a target to diagnose HCMV¹.

Finally, an outer lipid bilayer surrounding viral and cellular glycoproteins⁵. These viral glycoproteins are grouped together in four complexes: CI (gB), CII (gM/gN), CIII (gH/gL/gO), and the pentameric complex (gH/gL/pUL128/pUL130/pUL131A, along with 20 other uncharacterized putative, non-complex viral membrane proteins that may play a key role in the virus entry towards the target cell, virus transmission from cell to cell and the maturation of the virions⁶ (**Figure 1**)⁷.

Figure 1. CMV Virion Representation. CMV outer lipid bilayer is surrounded by viral and cellular glycoprotein complexes. gB (gC I complex), gM/gN (gC II complex), gH/gL/gO (gC III complex), and gH/gL/pUL128/pUL130/pUL131A (pentameric complex). The gC I, gC II and gC III complexes are essential for CMV entry in fibroblast and Langerhans cells, while the pentameric complex is required for CMV entry in epithelial, endothelial, and myeloid cells⁷.

1.1.3. Life cycle

CMV has a wide tropism and it is capable of infecting different cell types, such as smooth muscle cells, epithelial cells, endothelial cells, fibroblasts, mesenchymal cells, hepatocytes, granulocytes, neutrophils, macrophages, neurons, and stromal cells. During latency CMV can be found in myeloid line progenitors and CD34+ cells⁸.

CMV uses different entry mechanisms for entry into the host cell depending on the cell type⁹. The initial attachment of CMV to the cell may be mediated by the interaction between gM/gN and glycosaminoglycans on the cell membrane¹⁰. After the initial attachment in fibroblasts entry occurs through a pH-independent fusion that involves the interaction of gB and the trimer complex gH/gL/gO with integrins and an alpha receptor (PDGFR α). A new entry mechanism has been previously suggested for CMV cell-entry that utilize THY-1, a cargo protein of clathrin-independent endocytotic vesicles, to facilitate efficient entry into the cell by a macropinocytosis-like process⁷.

Cytomegalovirus entry into endothelial, epithelial and myeloid cells occurs due to the interaction of the CMV pentameric complex (gH/gL/pUL128-pUL130-pUL131a) and the cell receptor (more likely neuropilin 2) that trigger PC-mediated endocytosis⁷. The fusion of the virion envelope with cellular membranes is pH-dependent and occurs at the endosomal membrane, and gB and gH/gL/gO are thought to be involved. A new mechanism has also CD46-dependent entry pathway been recently identified, that involves cell membrane receptor CD46.

As a result of the different mechanisms nucleocapsid and tegument proteins are released into the cytoplasm of the infected cell¹¹, and the nucleocapsids are transported to the nucleus. The viral DNA is translocated into the nucleus, where the pp71 protein virus activates the expression of

immediate early genes IE1 and IE2. Both are responsible for recruiting RNA polymerase II from the host cell to transcribe the early (E) genes into special locations in the nucleus. The E genes proteins are responsible of the synthesis of the viral DNA (which starts 24 hours after infection and peaks at 48 hours) and the expression of the late (L) genes. The L genes conduct the synthesis of the structural proteins of the virion which, after assembly (starts at 48 hours and peaks at 72-96 hours approximately), allow the exit from the cell to continue the infection (**Figure 2**)¹.

Figure 2. CMV life cycle in a human cell. CMV enters in the cell by fusion or endocytosis depending on the cell type. Replication occurs in the nucleus and capsid formation after L genes translation. After encapsulation, viral envelope is acquiring in the assembly complex, and viral particles and dense bodies release the cell by exocytosis¹.

1.2. CMV Infection and Pathogenesis

Human cytomegalovirus is a highly prevalent herpesvirus, that affects approximately 60% of adults in developed countries while can reach up to 90-100% in developing countries¹².

Cytomegalovirus transmission can be horizontal when occurs through blood, tissue, or direct contact with the urine, saliva, vaginal secretions, semen, or breast milk of an infected person¹³. Transmission can also occur vertically, from mother to child at different stages during pregnancy or delivery¹⁴.

Human cytomegalovirus is usually asymptomatic in immunocompetent individuals or it may cause minor complications resulting in similar symptoms as infectious mononucleosis⁵. On the other hand, in immunocompromised patients such as HIV infected patients and transplant recipients CMV infection can be associated with severe symptoms causing a high morbidity and mortality¹⁵.

1.2.1. Infection and risk factors in Solid Organ Transplant (SOT) recipients

Despite major advances in antiviral treatments, CMV infection retains a significant impact on graft morbidity and survival in SOT recipients. CMV syndrome can manifest with symptoms such as fever and malaise often associated with leukopenia or thrombocytopenia¹⁶. While invasive tissue disease affects the transplanted organ due to graft dysfunction associated with immune rejection. The target and progression of CMV infection and disease varies depending upon various risk factors¹⁷.

The risk of developing CMV disease in SOT patients depends on diverse factors, including the CMV serostatus of the donor and transplant recipient, the type of organ transplanted, the prevention treatment and the overall immunosuppression status of the patient, among others¹⁶. Regarding the CMV serostatus, patients at higher risk for CMV infection are seronegative recipients that have no previous immunity against CMV and receive a graft from a seropositive (D+/R-) donor. Medium risk are those seropositive recipients and patients at lower risk for developing CMV infection are seronegative recipients who receive a seronegative (D-/R-) graft¹⁶, unless they receive blood transfusions from seropositive recipients or exhibit a primary infection¹⁸.

As for organ type and post-transplant period, lung, bowel, and pancreas transplant recipients present a higher risk for CMV infection than kidney, liver, and heart transplant recipients. The main reason may be the higher intensity of immunosuppression and the increased amount of lymphoid tissue involved in such transplants, so the likelihood of acquiring monocytes and other CMV-infected lymphoid cells that are latent or replicating is higher¹⁶.

Finally, immunosuppressive treatments are essential to prevent graft rejection and to avoid specific humoral and cellular responses to the graft, but at the same time, it promotes uncontrolled replication of latent CMV and increases the risk of disease. The level of immunosuppression is influenced by many factors such as dose, duration and type of immunosuppressant, basal disease of the adaptive immune system, age or the development of comorbidities¹⁹.

1.3. Immune response against CMV

CMV is effectively controlled in healthy individuals, suggesting a balance between the virus and the host immune response that allows the virus to persist sub-clinically. However, in certain situations such as immunosuppression where this balance is altered, uncontrolled CMV replication occurs and therefore, immunosuppressed individuals are at higher risk of CMV infection or reactivation. Immune control of CMV involves the combination of both immune system responses: innate and adaptive (cellular and humoral). Protection against CMV infection is usually due to cell-mediated immune response, mainly T cells and NK cells, considered as the preeminent components of the immune system against CMV infection^{20,21}. Nevertheless, several recent studies have suggested the crucial role that

the humoral response plays in protecting against CMV disease, specially pointing towards the importance of antibody-mediated response in viral infection²².

1.3.1. The role of neutralizing antibodies in humoral response

The role of antibody-mediated response in CMV immunity remains still a matter of debate²³. CMV infection induces the production of IgM, IgA and IgG immunoglobulins. While IgM and IgA antibodies may persist for 2-8 months and up to one year respectively, IgG antibodies persist for life, increasing in antibody titers after successive reactivations²⁴. Immunoglobulin G antibodies directed to CMV envelope glycoproteins capable of blocking infection are identified as neutralizing antibodies. Nevertheless, the role of neutralizing antibodies in SOT recipients and their acquisition kinetics after primary infection are poorly characterized. A limitation of the studies conducted to date is that most neutralizing antibody studies have been performed *in vitro* on cellular models of CMV infection using fibroblasts, although during *in vivo* infection the first barrier to natural CMV infection are epithelial and endothelial cells. Thus, the use of fibroblasts may not be fully identifying the entire spectrum of neutralizing antibodies in CMV infection. In addition, recent studies indicate higher titers of neutralizing antibodies after CMV infection in epithelial or endothelial cells compared to infection in fibroblasts, being observed 48 times higher neutralizing activity²⁵. Likewise, in SOT recipients, this has been associated with higher protection against CMV infection and disease, as well as, a reduction in treatment days after CMV infection in epithelial cells than in fibroblasts²².

Passive immunization also plays a crucial role in CMV immunity in SOT recipients. A meta-analysis study for 698 SOT recipients suggested an increase in overall survival and the reduction of CMV disease and infection after hyperimmunoglobulin administration therapy²⁶. Despite the favourable results, the utilization of this therapy in SOT patients is still questionable and the presence of antiviral prophylaxis as suitable options⁷.

1.4. Prevention and treatment of CMV infection

As a result of progress made in CMV prevention strategies, there has been a decrease in CMV-related mortality. The two strategies recommended to prevent CMV disease in transplant recipients are universal prophylaxis and preemptive therapy based on the CMV viremia monitoring.

Universal prophylaxis involves the administration of antiviral treatment to all patients at risk of CMV infection immediately after transplantation and is continued for a period ranging from 3 to 6 months, depending on the serostatus of the donor and the recipient, as well as, the type of organ transplanted. Intravenous ganciclovir and oral valganciclovir are considered first-line drugs²⁷. However, the use of this prophylactic strategy is associated with disadvantages such as toxicity caused by antiviral treatment and the incidence of late CMV disease that occurs after the end of the

prophylactic period²⁸. On the other hand, due to the generalised use of ganciclovir, various CMV strains have developed resistance mutations to this antiviral²⁹.

The preemptive treatment strategy consists in administering antiviral treatment only when viral replication is detected, above a defined threshold. This advance strategy involves regular monitoring and follow-up of patients and determination of viral loads. In those patients with a positive CMV viral load, antiviral treatment is established, avoiding the progression of the infection which is discontinued once viral replication is no longer detected, avoiding adverse effects of long lasting treatments such as the toxicity and the associated cost. In addition, controlled exposure to the virus, triggers the development of specific cellular immunity in patients, which translates into a lower incidence of CMV disease³⁰. Nevertheless, one of its main disadvantages is the high cost of monitoring patients and the increased patient follow-up that required good coordination. In addition, it does not protect the patient from other infections or other indirect effects associated with CMV exposure³¹.

Both treatment strategies have advantages and disadvantages, and there are variations in their clinical application between different health centres. However, both have been shown to be effective in preventing CMV infection and disease³².

1.5. Vaccines

Due to the severity of CMV infection and the high number of deaths associated to this pathogen, at the beginning of the 21st century the American Institute of Medicine proposed the development of a vaccine as prime concern for CMV prevention³³.

Over the past several years, numerous attempts have been made to develop vaccines against CMV, however none have met the criteria of an ideal vaccine for clinical use³⁴. Throughout the pre-clinical and clinical trials awareness of the difficulties associated with the development of a vaccine has been considered due to the complex interaction between CMV and the immune system and the absence of an animal model able to reproduce human physiology associated to CMV infection³⁵.

The ideal CMV vaccine should be able to mimic the effect produced by the natural infection, both; cellular and humoral response are important in preventing CMV disease. While the fundamental role of cell-mediated immunity for vaccine design has been reviewed elsewhere^{36,37}, little is known about the efficiency of antibody-mediated immunity and it may play a critical role in CMV protection⁷.

1.5.1 CMV antigens that induce antibody-mediated immunity

An ideal vaccine should contain high titers of neutralizing antibodies able to block infection in various cell types. As previously described (1.1.3. Life cycle), four complexes (CI, CII, CIII, and the pentameric complex) and 20 other uncharacterized putative, non-complex viral membrane proteins, may be involved differently in CMV entry into endothelial, epithelial or fibroblast cells, and therefore,

neutralizing antibodies elicited by multiple antigens from different cells are needed for an ideal vaccine^{38,7}.

Multiple vaccines including the glycoproteins gB (the most researched envelope protein), gH and the pentameric complex, either separately or in combination, have been tested positively and passed to clinical trials^{39,40,41}. Moreover, gM/gN, complex is also considered a potential vaccine candidate due to strong neutralizing antibody generated from epithelial, endothelial and fibroblast cells⁴². In addition, a vaccine at phase II clinical trial based on recombinant gB prepared with MF59 adjuvant revealed, that gB contribute to the stimulation of neutralizing antibodies and provide at least partial protection against CMV infection⁴⁰.

The envelope glycoprotein gH is present in three of the viral membrane complexes. Antibodies against different epitopes on gH have demonstrated moderate neutralizing activity of fibroblasts, epithelial, and endothelial cells, while antibodies against epitopes of other proteins of the pentameric complex demonstrate potent neutralization of infection in macrophages, epithelial and endothelial cells, but not fibroblasts^{26,43}. In fact, vaccines employing gH/gL and the pentameric complex are currently in preclinical studies, including viral vectors and nucleic acid vaccines⁴⁴.

Thus, taking into consideration the research done so far, the ideal vaccine against CMV infection may include a combination of multiple antigens inducing strong neutralizing antibodies for epithelial, endothelial and fibroblast cells in addition to inducing a potent cellular immune response. Hence, efforts should be made on searching for possible CMV antigens able to elicit a complete protective immune response.

2. OBJECTIVES

Despite the effort of the last years, no vaccine has yet met the criteria of an ideal vaccine for clinical use. In view of these drawbacks, the main aim of this work is to identify and characterize CMV antigens that induces an antibody immune response in patients that have developed high neutralizing antibody titers in response to CMV infection after transplantation, for vaccine design. To achieve these objectives, the following partial objectives have been set:

1. Identify CMV antigens recognized by serum samples from immunized patients that exhibit a high neutralizing antibody response.
2. Characterization of the CMV proteins using proteomic approaches.
3. Demonstration of protein recognition through protein expression and immune recognition *in vitro*.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Serum collection

Serum samples from 29 kidney transplant recipients collected at a University Hospital in Spain were tested. One sample was collected at transplantation (baseline) and the second sample (post-immunization) after acquiring high (1/640) neutralizing antibody titers. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients and protocols were approved by the local Ethics Committee for Clinical Research.

3.2. Cells, media and virus

MRC-5 are human fetal lung fibroblasts (ATCC CCL-171) and HEK 293-T are human embryonic kidney cells (ATCC CRL-11268). Both were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC; Manassas, VA). The MRC-5 cells and HEK 293-T were cultured in high glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium-DMEM (Gibco-BRL) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (HyClone Laboratories), 10,000 IU/L penicillin and 10 mg/L streptomycin (Gibco-BRL)⁴⁵.

TOP-10 *Escherichia coli* XL10 Gold ultracompetent bacterial strain was used for plasmid transformation and antibiotic selection was done in LB agar media (Conda) with Ampicillin 100 µg/ml (Amp, A0166-5G, Sigma). S.O.C medium (Invitrogen) was used following heat-shock of the bacterial competent cells.

CMV strain used in this study, BADrUL131-Y4, was provided by Dr. Thomas Shenk (Princeton University) is a derivative of a BAC clone of the AD169 strain that includes a Green Fluorescence Protein (GFP).

3.3. Western Blot analysis

3.3.1. Protein quantification by Bradford assay

MRC-5 cells in 75-cm² flasks (T75) were infected with CMV strain BADrUL131-Y4 at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 1 and were incubated for 72 hours at 37 °C in 5% CO₂, until reaching 80-95% confluency

Infected cells were recovered from the plate and were centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The cell pellets were resuspended in 500 µl of 1X lysis buffer (Cell Signaling Technology) and incubated on ice for 5 min. Cell lysates were used for protein quantification by the Bradford method.

Standard curve for protein quantitation was determined by Bradford with increasing concentrations (2µg/mL-25 µg/mL) using a 2 mg/ml bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Bio-Rad) stock solution. One µL of each of the standard dilution was added to a cuvette containing 200 µL of the Bradford 1X dye reagent (Bio-Rad) and 800 µL of distilled H₂O. As a blank, 1 µL of lysis buffer was used.

3.3.2. Western Blotting

We first optimized the amount of protein required for Western blot analysis. Increasing concentrations, from 10 μg to 70 μg , of CMV-infected cell protein lysate were prepared. Briefly, each of the concentration were mixed with 4X Laemmli loading buffer (Bio-Rad) and incubated at 95 °C for 5 minutes to denature the proteins. Denatured proteins were separated by electrophoresis on a 7.5% SDS-PAGE gel (*Sodium Dodecylsulfate-Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis*). Acrylamide gels were stained using Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 (Sigma-Aldrich Co.) reagent to visualize the proteins. On each gel, 5 μl of Precision Plus Protein Dual Color Standards (Bio-Rad Laboratories) was used as molecular weight marker.

Once the protein concentration was optimized, after SDS-PAGE electrophoresis, proteins were blotted onto nitrocellulose membranes (Bio-Rad) by a semi dry method (Trans-Blot® SD Semi-Dry Electrophoretic Transfer Cell, Bio-Rad) at 25 volts for 30 minutes to ensure the correct transfer of the proteins. For this purpose, the membrane and the transfer papers were first wetted in 1X transfer buffer (39 mM glycine + 48 mM Tris Base + 0.037% SDS + 10% methanol) and a "sandwich" was prepared, placing the membrane in direct contact with the gel and several layers of transfer paper soaked in 1X transfer buffer above and below the gel and the membrane. These layers were then located between two plates that form an anode (+) and a cathode (-) when an electric field is applied, as shown in the figure below (**Figure 3**)⁴⁶. Transfer efficiency was assessed by staining the gel with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250.

Figure 3. Model of a semi-dry transfer. The membrane and the transfer papers were first wetted in 1X transfer buffer and a "sandwich" was prepared, placing the membrane in direct contact with the gel and several layers of transfer paper soaked in 1X transfer buffer above and below the gel and the membrane⁴⁶.

To avoid unspecific binding of the proteins with the antibody, the membrane was blocked with blocking buffer (1X PBS + 0.1% Tween 20 + 5% skim milk) for one hour at room temperature, under agitation. Membranes were probed with the primary antibodies, in our case patient serum samples at a 1:200 dilution in blocking buffer (1X PBS + 0.1% Tween 20 + 5% skim milk) and incubated at 4 °C overnight, under agitation. The following day, membranes were washed five times with wash buffer

(1X PBS + 0.1% Tween 20) for 5 minutes each. Horseradish peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody Goat Anti-Human IgG (Abcam) was added at a 1:2000 dilution in blocking buffer (1X PBS + 0.1% Tween 20 + 5% skim milk) and incubated at room temperature for one hour, under agitation. Membranes were washed five times with wash buffer (1X PBS + 0.1% Tween 20) for 5 minutes each. Bands were visualized with enhanced chemiluminescence using the Super Signal™ West Pico Chemiluminescent Substrate detection Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific), following the manufacturer's recommendations and the images were captured on a ChemiDoc Touch Imaging System (Bio-Rad). A schematic of the western blot protocol is shown in **Figure 4**⁴⁶.

Figure 4. Western Blotting or immunoblotting protocol⁴⁶.

3.4. Protein identification by Liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

Protein bands that were specifically detected only by the post-immune serum were cleaved from a polyacrylamide gel and identified by liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). Optimization of the polyacrylamide percentage was performed to ensure separation of the protein of interest according to their molecular weight. Thus, the lower the percentage of polyacrylamide, the larger the pore size, and the better separation of larger proteins, and vice versa.

After optimizing the percentage of polyacrylamide for each case, successive western blotting was carried out, following the same protocol described previously, and the protein bands of interest were cut with a scalpel, previously stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250.

Proteomic analysis was performed using LC-MS/MS in the proteomics facility of SCSIE University of Valencia. A schematic of the process is shown in **Figure 5**.

Firstly, an "In-gel" digestion of the protein bands was performed. The gel fraction was cut and the samples were digested with sequencing grade trypsin (Promega), as described previously⁴⁷. 100-200 ng of trypsin in 50 μ L of ABC solution was used. The digestion was stopped with TFA (1% final concentration), a double extraction with ACN was done and all the peptide solutions and dried in a rotatory evaporator. Samples were re suspended with 10-30 μ L of 2% ACN (Acetonitrile); 0.1% TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid).

For the LC-MS/MS analysis, five μ L of the digested mixture sample was loaded onto a trap column (3 μ C18-CL 120 Å, 350 μ m x 0.5mm; Eksigent) and desalted with 0.1% TFA at 5 μ L min⁻¹ for 5 min. Peptides were loaded onto an analytical column (LC Column 3 μ C18-CL 120 Å, 0.075 x 150 mm; Eksigent) equilibrated in 5% acetonitrile 0.1% FA (formic acid). Peptide elution was carried out with a linear gradient of 7-40% B in A for 20 min. (A: 0.1% FA; B: ACN, 0.1% FA) at a flow rate of 300 nL min⁻¹. Peptides were analysed in a nanoESI qTOF mass spectrometer (6600plus TripleTOF, ABSCIEX).

Sample was ionized in a Source Type: Optiflow < 1 uL Nano applying 3.0 kV to the spray emitter at 200 °C. Analysis was carried out in a data-dependent mode. Survey MS1 scans were acquired from 350–1400 m/z for 250 ms. The quadrupole resolution was set to 'LOW' for MS2 experiments, which were acquired 100–1500 m/z for 25 ms in 'high sensitivity' mode. Following switch criteria were used: charge: 2+ to 4+; minimum intensity; 100 counts per second (cps). Up to 100 ions were selected for fragmentation after each survey scan. Dynamic exclusion was set to 15 s. The system sensitivity was controlled by analysing 500 ng of K562 trypsin digestion (Sciex), in these conditions 2260 proteins were identified (FDR <1%) in 45 minutes gradient.

The LC-MS/MS information was sent to search the SwissProt, the *Herpesviridae* Uniprot database (82000 proteins) and *herpesviridae* NCBI database (290000 proteins) with the Paragon

algorithm of the ProteinPilot software, v. 5.0 with the following parameters: trypsin specificity, IAM cys-alkylation, taxonomy no restricted, and the search effort set to rapid with FDR analysis.

LC-MS/MS analysis is shown schematically in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. Steps of the proteomic study using Liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

3.5. Cloning and Protein expression in HEK 293-T cells

3.5.1. Gene amplification and cloning

The open reading frame (ORF) of the gene encoding the identified protein candidates were amplified by PCR with the Phusion DNA polymerase (ThermoScientific), using specific primers (ThermoFisher Scientific).

PCR products were separated by electrophoresis in a 1% agarose (Conda) gel, supplemented with Gel Red™ (Biotium) and the PCR product bands were visualized under UV light using the ChemiDoc Imaging System (Bio-Rad Laboratories). The size of the DNA fragments were estimated comparing with GeneRuler DNA Ladder Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

The amplified products were cloned in a pcDNA™3.1/myc-His(-) (5.5 kb) vector (Invitrogen), designed for overproduction of recombinant proteins in mammalian cell lines (**Figure 6**)⁴⁸. To construct the pcDNA-based plasmid expressing the desired gene, the complete ORF was amplified from the HCMV BADrUL131-Y4 BAC. Briefly, the PCR products and pcDNA, previously quantified using the Eppendorf BioSpectrometer at 280 nm (Eppendorf), were both digested with 10X FastDigest buffer

along the corresponding restriction enzyme (Thermo Scientific). The reaction was incubated for 10 mins at 37 °C. All products were then purified with the NZY GelPure kit (GelPure, NZYTech), following the manufacturer's recommendations.

Figure 6. Map of pcDNATM3.1/myc-His(-) A, B, and C (5.5 kb) vector (Invitrogen)⁴⁸.

Molar concentration of the vector and insert were calculated using the NEBioCalculator tool <https://nebiocalculator.neb.com> and were mixed in a 5:1 molar ratio. The ligation reaction was carried out by adding 1 µl T4 DNA ligase (Thermo Scientific), 2 µl ligase buffer in a 20 µl total volume and the mixture was incubated for 5 mins at 37 °C. 10-100 ng of the ligation reaction were transformed into *E. coli* XL10 Gold ultracompetent cells, often used to transform large DNA molecules with high efficiency, which were mixed carefully and the reaction was set on ice for 30 mins. Cells were then heated at 42 °C for 30 seconds and immediately set up on ice for 2 mins to cool down. After transformation, 150 µl of pre-warmed S.O.C media (Invitrogen) was added to the cells and they were incubated for 1 hour at 37°C without agitation, for recovery. After an hour, the bacterial suspensions were inoculated in LB plate (Conda) with ampicillin 100 µg/ml (A0166-5G, Sigma) and incubated overnight, at 37°C. The positive clones were verified by ampicillin selection and colony PCR. For colony PCR, a colony growth in a LB plate with ampicillin was added to 50 µl of NaOH 20 mM. The mixture was heated at 95°C for 5 minutes and then centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 1 minute. 1 µl of the supernatant was used for PCR amplification. To confirm amplification, PCR products were analysed on 1% agarose (Conda) gel electrophoresis. The positive clones were inoculated in 5 ml LB with 100 µg/ml ampicillin and incubated overnight at 37°C

and 150 rpm. The next day, 900 µl of cell culture were inoculated in a cryotube with 500 µl glycerol (100 %) and stored at -80°C. Plasmid extractions were performed using the NZYMiniprep kit (NZYMiniprep, NZYTech), following the manufacturer's instructions and were sequenced to confirm the correct insertion.

3.5.2 Transfection into HEK 293-T cells

Plasmid encoding the proteins of interest were transfected into the human cell line HEK 293-T by using Cl_2Ca 250 mM. The day before the transfection, HEK 293-T cells were seeded in a 6-well plate, with 500,000 cells/well. Transfection was carried out the next day, when 50-60% confluence was reached. Briefly, 4 hours before transfection DMEM medium was replaced with fresh medium and 200 µl of Cl_2Ca and 4-8 µg of the vector were diluted individually. 200 µl of HBS buffer saline (140 mM NaCl, 1.5 mM Na_2HPO_4 , 50 mM HEPES) was added and was incubated for 1 minute at room temperature. Subsequently, the mixture was added to each well containing cells and medium, and gently mixed by rocking the plate. After 24 hours of transfection, DMEM medium was replaced with fresh medium. Transfected cells were incubated during 48 hours at 37°C in a 5% CO_2 incubator.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Study population. Neutralizing titers induced by natural infection.

We used a cohort of patients that are currently being studied in the laboratory in collaboration with a major Hospital in Madrid. These patients are kidney transplant recipients that are follow up after transplantation during one year and are monitored to detect episodes of CMV replication as well as CMV specific immune response, both neutralizing antibodies (Nab) and T-cell immune response, at baseline (day of the transplant) and at 3, 6 and 12 months after transplantation.

Of the 29 kidney transplant recipients analysed, 11 were seronegative for CMV, with no neutralizing antibody titers or CMV-specific T-cell response at baseline, while the other 18 patients had low neutralizing antibody titers. In both groups, all patients developed high neutralizing antibody (NAb) titers and all post-immune serum samples used had titers $>1/640$, determined by micro-neutralization assay as previously described⁴⁵. The neutralizing antibody titer was defined as the titer of the patient's serum that reduced virus infectivity by 50% in comparison to an infected control. Information regarding the CMV-specific T-cell immune response measured using intracellular cytokine staining was also available where 23 patients were negative at baseline and all patients were positive at the time that the post-immune serum sample was collected.

Serum sample information on CMV-specific immune response (neutralizing antibody titers, and T-cell immunity), and dates collected for each of the patients included (1-29) are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Information on CMV-specific immune response (neutralizing antibody titers, and T-cell immunity), and dates collected for each of the 29 patients analysed.

*ND: Not determined

Serum	NAbs titers (Baseline)	T-cell immunity (Baseline)	NAbs titers (Post-immunity)	T-cell immunity (Post-immunity)
1	0 (29-Jul-08)	Neg	2560 (18-Sep-09)	Pos
2	0 (28-Oct-08)	Neg	2560 (22-Jun-09)	Pos
3	0 (09-Mar-09)	Neg	2560 (09-Jul-09)	Pos
4	0 (13-Jan-10)	Neg	2560 (22-Nov-10)	Pos
5	0 (29-Jun-10)	Neg	2560 (10-May-11)	Pos
6	0 (03-Jun-09)	Neg	1280 (04-Dec-09)	Pos
7	0 (24-Apr-07)	Neg	2560 (02-May-08)	Pos
8	0 (07-Oct-09)	Neg	2560 (03-Jul-10)	Pos
9	0 (22-Dec-09)	Neg	2560 (01-Oct-10)	Pos
10	0 (17-Mar-08)	Neg	640 (07-Oct-08)	Pos
11	0 (16-May-11)	Neg	640 (24-Nov-11)	Pos
12	5 (18-Feb-08)	Neg	1280 (30-Sep-08)	Pos
13	5 (23-Apr-15)	Pos	2560 (11-Nov-15)	Pos
14	5 (07-Oct-16)	Pos	2560 (03-Apr-17)	Pos
15	5 (12-May-10)	Neg	2560 (14-Oct-10)	Pos
16	5 (30-Dec-10)	Neg	2560 (03-Jun-11)	Pos
17	20 (03-Sep-08)	Neg	2560 (09-Sep-09)	Pos
18	40 (03-Nov-15)	ND	640 (09-May-16)	Pos
19	40 (17-Aug-18)	Pos	640 (21-Feb-19)	Pos
20	40 (26-Dec-07)	Neg	1280 (19-Feb-08)	Pos
21	80 (11-Apr-18)	Neg	640 (10-Oct-18)	Pos
22	80 (23-Apr-19)	Neg	640 (28-Nov-19)	Pos
23	80 (08-May-16)	ND	1280 (04-Nov-16)	Pos
24	80 (28-Aug-18)	Neg	1280 (08-Mar-19)	Pos
25	80 (04-Apr-11)	Pos	2560 (06-Sep-11)	Pos
26	80 (09-Jul-07)	Neg	2560 (19-Nov-07)	Pos
27	80 (27-Apr-17)	ND	2560 (10-Oct-17)	Pos
28	80 (19-Mar-16)	ND	2560 (03-Oct-16)	Pos
29	640 (12-Jan-17)	ND	1280 (07-Jul-17)	Pos

Despite the development of new diagnostic techniques and the advantages provided by different treatment strategies, CMV infection retains a significant impact on graft morbidity after transplantation. Seronegative (R-) transplant recipients who receive an organ from a seropositive (D+) patient have a higher chance of developing CMV infection compared to transplants performed in other serological combinations.

Seronegative (R-) patients for CMV, with no neutralizing antibody titers or CMV-specific T-cell response, can be considered an ideal study population to examine CMV infection as well as CMV specific immune response for various reasons. Firstly, these patients have not developed previous CMV infection and therefore have no CMV specific immune response, both neutralizing antibodies (Nab)

and T-cell immune response. In addition, around 60% of them develop primary infection during the first year after transplantation due to discontinuation of prophylaxis²⁸, and therefore, specific immunity to CMV can be characterized *de novo*. A limitation however is the low incidence of high-risk transplantation (D+/R-), which makes it considerably difficult to include patients in this type of studies. Nevertheless, in our study we have included 11 patients that were seronegative for CMV, with no neutralizing antibody titers or CMV-specific T-cell response at baseline and, as observed in **Table 1**, one year after transplantation specific immunity to CMV has been developed and with neutralizing antibody (NAb) titers >1/640.

Thus, this study population would be ideal to examine the parameters of the immune response that are related to protection against CMV infection and disease.

4.2. Detection of CMV proteins recognized by patient serum samples with high neutralizing antibody titers

With the goal to search for CMV proteins that induce an antibody immune response in the selected patients, western blot analysis was carried out to detect CMV antigens with the following criteria:

1. Antigens recognized by antibodies present in the post-immunity serum that were not recognized by the baseline serum (in patients with no neutralizing antibodies at baseline).
2. Antigens recognized by antibodies present in the pre-immune serum, from patients with low titers at baseline, at low levels that increased in the post-immune serum detection.

As a source of CMV proteins, CMV-infected cell lysates were used (**Figure 7**), and to detect unspecific binding to cellular proteins were present in the mixture, a mock-infected control was used.

Figure 7. MRC-5 cells infected with CMV strain BADrUL131-Y4 at a MOI of 1 for 72 hours.

CMV infected cell lysates were quantified by Bradford using the following BSA Standard curve (Figure 8).

Figure 8. BSA Standard curve.

The amount of protein required for western blot analysis was optimized preparing increasing concentrations of proteins from 10 μg to 70 μg , of CMV-infected cell lysate (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Protein bands at different concentrations (10-70 μg) stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250.

60 μg of protein was considered optimal and were used for western blot using serum samples as primary antibodies. *Western blotting* results are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Detection of CMV viral proteins by *western blotting*. In the top of each image the patient number, and the serum used are indicated. M indicates the lane were the molecular marker was loaded. **A.** Patients that have no neutralizing antibodies at baseline (patients 01-10). **B.** Patients who had low neutralizing antibody titers (patients 12-29)

Figure 10. Detection of CMV viral proteins by western blotting. In the top of each image the patient number, and the serum used are indicated. M indicates the lane where the molecular marker was loaded. **A.** Patients that have no neutralizing antibodies at baseline (patients 01-10). **B.** Patients who had low neutralizing antibody titers (patients 12-29)

Figure 10. Detection of CMV viral proteins by *western blotting*. In the top of each image the patient number, and the serum used are indicated. M indicates the lane were the molecular marker was loaded. **A.** Patients that have no neutralizing antibodies at baseline (patients 01-10). **B.** Patients who had low neutralizing antibody titers (patients 12-29)

As shown in **Figure 10**, several proteins with different molecular weights were detected.

As expected, no proteins were recognized using the pre-immunity serum from patients with no baseline antibody titers (**Figure 10A pre-immunity lane, bands are labelled by arrows**). While some protein bands with low intensity were recognized using the pre-immunity serum from patients with low baseline antibody titers (**Figure 10B pre-immunity lane**), as clearly shown in patient 29, as an example.

Of the proteins identified we selected fourteen proteins with molecular weight ranging approximately from 30 to 280 kilodaltons (kDa) that met the criteria.

In patients with no baseline neutralizing antibody-mediated immunity (**Figure 10A**), bands (shown by arrows) are not observed in the lane corresponding to the pre-immunity sera. However, in the same patient in the lane corresponding to the post-immunity serum significant labelling can be observed. Some of these bands that were also observed in the mock-infected lysate used as controls, were discarded. Nevertheless, significant labelling is observed in patients 7 and 10 in the lane corresponding to the pre-immunity sera, this may be due to an incorrect data determined by micro-neutralization. In short, these results suggest that these patients have developed a CMV-specific antibody-mediated immunity *de novo* that recognize a wide range of viral proteins.

In the group of patients with baseline neutralizing antibody titers, ranging from 1/5 to 1/640 (**Figure 10B**), in those patients with low titers, such as 1/5 and 1/20 (patients 12-17), had a similar pattern that patients in **Figure 10A**, with no bands detected in the pre-immunity serum suggesting that a minimum titer is necessary for the recognition by western blot. However, in patients with titers above 1/40, bands were already visible using the pre-immune serum although the labelling significantly increased using the post-immunity serum which correlated with higher antibody titers.

We detected band patterns that were slightly disparate between different patients however, having higher titers was not related with the number of bands detected. In fact, using serum samples from individuals with the same neutralizing antibody titer detected such disparate bands and intensities. This result suggest that CMV-infection was different in these patients probably due to a difference in the number of replication episodes or peak viral load of each episode eliciting a distinct immune response. In addition, antibodies present in patient's sera are a complex mixture of neutralizing and non-neutralizing antibodies with diverse functions. In general, using serum with higher titers (i.e. 1/640, 1/1280 and 1/2560) resulted in higher intensity of the bands recognized.

We further analysed the protein pattern obtained in both groups of patients. In **Figure 11** is shown a representation of the patterns obtained. Patients analysed are shown in the upper part and on the right the size of the proteins with their molecular weight in decreasing order. The intensity of the bands obtained are also shown in different shades of blue.

Figure 11. Representation of the protein pattern obtained in both groups of patients. Patients analysed are shown in the upper part and on the right the size of the proteins with their molecular weight in decreasing order. The intensity of the bands obtained are also shown in different shades of blue.

Proteins with a higher molecular weight, above 200 kDa, are generally not very abundant, in both groups, with no baseline neutralizing antibody and those who present low neutralizing antibody titers. Predicted proteins of approximately 70, 95, 125 and 155 kDa were observed mostly in the group of patients with antibody titers at baseline. Predicted proteins of approximately 40, 45, 55 and 65 kDa were the most abundant in both groups. Surprisingly, no protein bands were observed in patients 3, 11 and 14 although post-immunity sera present high neutralizing antibody titers $>1/640$.

Together, these results show that using serum of immunized patients is an excellent strategy to identify CMV proteins that may be involved on stimulating an antibody-mediated immunity and may be used for vaccine design.

4.3. Identification of CMV proteins by LC-MS/MS

Before cutting the bands from the acrylamide gel, optimization of the polyacrylamide percentage was performed to ensure separation of the protein of interest according to their molecular weight.

Preparation of the gels at different concentrations of polyacrylamide are shown in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12. SDS-PAGE polyacrylamide gels prepared at A: 6.5 %, B: 10%, C: 13% and D: 15% stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250.

The identified proteins were characterized using a proteomic approach using LC-MS/MS analysis. The MS/MS information was sent to search the SwissProt, the *Herpesviridae* Uniprot database and the *Herpesviridae* NCBI database, and the results are listed in **Table 2**

Table 2. HCMV proteins identified by LC-MS/MS.

N	%Cov(95)	Peptides(95%)	Database Accession	Gene	Mol. Mass (kDa)	Protein name
1	21.940	6	P16790	UL44	46	DNA polymerase processivity factor
2	9.817	13	P16785	UL48	253	Large tegument protein deneddylase
3	15.690	16	P16729	UL86	153	Major capsid protein
4	23.160	23	P17147	UL57	133	Major DNA-binding protein
5	47.280	49	P09715	IRS1	91	Protein IRS1
6	51.480	48	P16784	UL47	110	Inner tegument protein
7	31.980	35	P09695	TRS1	83	Tegument protein TRS1
8	32.010	22	P06473	UL55	102	Envelope glycoprotein B (gB)
9	66.670	44	P06725	UL83	65	65 kDa phosphoprotein (pp65)
10	25.830	19	P16782	UL45	101	Ribonucleoside-diphosphate reductase large subunit-like protein
11	32.250	21	P16727	UL84	65	Protein UL84
12	27.590	13	P19893	UL122	62	Viral transcription factor IE2

Of the 14 bands analysed twelve different CMV proteins that showed statistically significant peptide identifications (peptides identified at a confidence level of 95% or higher). Multiple identifications per band were detected, resulting in a total of 12 viral proteins encoded by known HCMV ORFs. The viral proteins identified included 4 tegument proteins (UL48, UL47, UL45 and UL83), a capsid protein (UL86), a glycoprotein (gB) and 6 proteins are required in DNA replication and transcription (UL44, IRS1, TRS1, UL57, UL84 and UL122).

UL44, UL84 and UL57 are indispensable for cytomegalovirus DNA replication. UL44 is a polymerase accessory protein and UL57 is a DNA binding protein that plays critical role in viral infection. In addition to participating in the initiation of replication by interacting with the origin-binding protein, it also reduces errors associated with DNA polymerase during elongation⁴⁹. On the other hand, UL84 initiates lytic DNA replication by interacting with oriLyt⁵⁰. IRS1 and TRS1 inhibit both viral and cellular protein synthesis⁵¹. The UL122 gene or IE2 protein plays a critical function as it is considered a preeminent HCMV regulatory protein. It participates in transcriptional activation of viral and host genes, besides regulation of various cellular activities⁵².

UL47 is an inner tegument protein and participates in capsid assembly. In addition, UL86 is highly conserved and along with UL48 forms the icosahedral capsid surrounded by a tegument formed by different proteins and all encompassed by a double lipid membrane of infectious virions and non-infectious enveloped particles⁵³.

UL83 encodes late expression proteins that are responsible of the structural proteins of the virions. 65 kDa phosphoprotein or pp65 is highly antigenic, promotes a cellular response, mainly from T cells⁵⁴, hence it is used as a target to diagnose HCMV¹. UL55 or envelope glycoprotein gB is one of the 4 glycoprotein complexes involved in cells infection by cytomegalovirus. The gB protein (Complex I) is essential for virus entry into all cell types and is also one of the targets of neutralizing antibodies⁵⁵. Most of the vaccines developed that have reached clinical phases have been formulated using the gB glycoprotein of the viral envelope²⁵ to promote a humoral response and the pp65 protein to promote a cellular response, mainly from T cells⁵⁴.

Some of these proteins such as UL83 (pp65) and UL55 (gB) have previously shown to elicit a potent antibody response. In addition, we also identified other 10 CMV proteins (UL44, UL47, UL48, UL57, UL84, UL86, UL122, IRS1, TRS1 and UL45) that induce an antibody response in patients that have developed a protective CMV-specific response after transplantation.

4.4 Amplification, Expression and Detection of CMV viral proteins

The open reading frame (ORF) of the gene encoding the identified protein candidates were amplified by PCR using specific primers (ThermoFisher Scientific).

The forward and reverse primers of the identified protein candidates are listed in **Table 3**, each of the primers also included at the 5`end a specific sequence of the restriction sites used for cloning into the desired plasmid.

Table 3. Primers used for gene amplification. Restriction-enzyme cut sites are underlined and the homologous sequence to the gene is shown in bold

Gene	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer	Size (bp)
UL44	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGCATGGATCGCAAGACGCG CCT	CGGGGTACCCGAGCCGCAC TTTTGCTTCTT GG	1302
UL48	CCGGAAT <u>TC</u> CGGCATGAAAGTCACACAGGC CAG	CCGGAAT <u>TC</u> CGGCCAAAAGATAGAGAAACC GCA	6726
UL86	CCGGAAT <u>TC</u> CGGATGGAGAACTGGTCGGCG CT	CGGGGTACCCGACGAGTTAAATAACATGG ATT	4113
UL47	CCGGAAT <u>TC</u> CGGCATGATGGCGAGGCGCAC GGT	CGGGGTACCCGATGGCGAGGCCGGCGGCA GGG	2952
UL57	AAATATGCGGCGCTATAAAATGAGCCACGA GGAACTAAC	CGCGATCCGCGTCAACCGGCTGCGTTTGGC CG	3708
IRS1	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGCATGGCCCAGCGCAACGG CAT	CGGGGTACCCGAATGATGAACGTGGTGAG GGG	2541
TRS1	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGGCCCAGCGCAACGGC AT	CGGGGTACCCGATTAAGCATTGTAATGATA AT	2367
UL84	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGGCCCAGGGTGGACCC AA	CGGGGTACCCGACAGGTGCGCCGACACCAT GG	1758
UL122	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGGAGAGCAGCGCCAAG AG	CGGGGTACCCGACTGGCTCTTGTTCCTCAG GT	1740
UL55	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGGAATCCAGGATCTGG TG	CGGGGTACCCGATCAGACGTTCTCTTCTTC GT	2721
UL45	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGAACCCCGCCGACGCC GA	CCGGAAT <u>TC</u> CGGTAGCTGGCGCAGTACTTGTA CA	2718
UL83	CCG <u>CTCGAG</u> CGGATGGAGTCGCGCGGTGCG CG	CGGGGTACCCGATCAACCTCGGTGCTTTTT GG	1686

To confirm protein detection, the open reading frames of the identified proteins were cloned into the pcDNA-based plasmid expressing UL44 (XhoI and KpnI), UL86 (EcoRI and KpnI), UL57 (NotI and BamHI), IRS1 (XhoI and KpnI), UL47 (EcoRI and KpnI), TRS1 (XhoI and KpnI), UL84 (XhoI and KpnI), UL122 (XhoI and KpnI), UL55 (XhoI and KpnI), UL83 (XhoI and KpnI), UL83 (XhoI and EcoRI) and UL48 (EcoRI and EcoRI). The identified proteins were individually expressed in HEK 293-T cells and expression of the protein was further detected by western blot using cell lysates of the CMV-infected cells as well as cell lysates of cells transfected with the individual CMV protein. For detection were used as primary antibody both, the baseline and the post-immunity serum sample from immunized patients.

Demonstration that the specific protein is recognized by antibodies present in the serum of immunized patients is shown in **Figure 13**. Cell lysates using mock infected MRC-5, mock infected HEK 293-T cells, 293-T cells transfected with the UL44 ORF, CMV-infected MRC-5 cells and the molecular weight marker (M) used are indicated. Panel on the left show staining of the protein lysates using Coomassie Brilliant blue staining and panel A and B western blots using the baseline pre-immune sera (A) and post-immune sera (B).

Figure 13. Demonstration of UL44 protein recognition through protein expression and immune recognition *in vitro*. Analysed samples (CMV cell lysate, UL44, MRC-5 and HEK 293-T cells) and the marker (M) are shown in the upper part, on the right the molecular weight marker with the approximate protein sizes and downwards the specification of the image detection method, Coomassie Brilliant Blue and Chemiluminescence. **A:** Baseline serum and **B:** Post-immunity serum of patient 23

As shown in **Figure 13**, we used patient 23 baseline and post-immunity serum to detect UL44 expression. A band corresponding to the right size (46 kDa) for protein UL44 was detected by the post-immune serum only in the lanes containing cell lysates from 293-T cells transfected with the UL44 ORF, CMV-infected MRC-5 cells. While no band was observed using the baseline serum (**Figure 13A**) or in lanes containing mock-infected cells lysate (MRC-5 and HEK 293-T) used as controls. Coomassie Brilliant Blue image is presented to visualize the proteins present in each sample.

We are currently detecting the expression of UL44 using other serums analysed in which previously proteins around 46 kDa were detected. Furthermore, we are in the process of cloning and expressing the resulting 11 proteins identified by LC-MS/MS.

The role of antibody-mediated response in CMV immunity remains still a matter of debate²³. In addition, the role of neutralizing antibodies in SOT recipients and their acquisition kinetics after primary infection are also poorly characterized. CMV presents a large genome with approximately 192 Open Reading Frames (ORFs) encoding for potential proteins, yet these proteins are hardly characterized and may be involved in stimulating an antibody-mediated and CMV-specific T-cell

immune response that could be used for vaccine design. For this reason, the use of techniques based on proteomics, transcriptomics, and genomics to individually characterize all the CMV antigens would be useful. In this study we have used a proteomic approach with LC-MS/MS analysis to identify CMV proteins that produce an antibody response aimed at neutralizing CMV infection for vaccine development. We have identified twelve different CMV proteins with molecular weights ranging from 30 to 280 kDa. Some of these proteins such as UL83 (pp65) and UL55 (gB) have previously shown to elicit a potent antibody response. In fact, most of the vaccines developed that have reached clinical phases have been formulated using the gB glycoprotein of the viral envelope²⁵ to promote a humoral response and the pp65 protein to promote a cellular response, mainly from T cells⁵⁴. Nonetheless, we have identified other 10 CMV proteins (UL44, UL47, UL48, UL57, UL84, UL86, UL122, IRS1, TRS1 and UL45) that induce an antibody response in patients that have developed a protective CMV-specific response after transplantation.

In previous works, neutralizing antibodies have been associated with protection against CMV primary infection, reactivation, and a decrease in the dissemination of viral loads⁵⁶. Besides, it has been suggested that CMV dissemination can be prevented with neutralizing antibodies present in serums from seropositive healthy donors for CMV⁵⁷. In fact, administration of CMV hyperimmunoglobulin improved overall survival, reduced CMV disease and deaths associated to this pathogen²⁶.

The ideal CMV vaccine should be able to mimic the effect produced by the natural infection, both; cellular and humoral response are important in preventing CMV disease. While the fundamental role of cell-mediated immunity for vaccine design has been reviewed elsewhere^{36,37}, little is known about the efficiency of antibody-mediated immunity and it may play a critical role in CMV protection⁷. Hence, efforts should be made on searching for possible CMV antigens able to elicit a complete protective immune response. The twelve potent CMV proteins identified in this work will require further investigation in animal models of immunization using these candidates for vaccine design.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Using serum of immunized patients is an excellent strategy to identify CMV proteins that are able to stimulate an antibody-mediated immunity and may also be involved in mediating a cellular response. Analysis using these candidates for vaccine design will be further investigated in animal models of immunization.

The present work has been submitted for Publication as a contribution of a Research Topic on “Immunity to Cytomegalovirus Infections: Challenges and Therapeutic Opportunities” in *Frontiers in Immunology*.

Your Research Topic abstract was accepted

Dear Dr Lalchandani-Lakhani,

Many thanks for contributing to the Research Topic "**Immunity to Cytomegalovirus Infections: Challenges and Therapeutic Opportunities**" with your abstract "Detection, Identification and Characterization of CMV Proteins Able to Induce a Strong Immune Response Using Serum Samples from Patients with Protective Immunity".

We are pleased to inform you that your abstract has been accepted by the Guest Editors. Congratulations on your achievement!

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INTRODUCTION

Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) is a highly prevalent herpesvirus, that affects approximately 60% of adults in developed countries while can reach up to 90-100% in developing countries. Due to the severity of CMV infection and the high number of deaths associated to this pathogen, the American Institute of Medicine proposed the development of a vaccine as a priority. Numerous attempts have been made to develop vaccines against CMV however, the complex interaction between CMV and the immune system and the absence of an animal model able to reproduce human physiology associated to CMV infection have hindered the development of a vaccine. In addition, many of the vaccine attempts failed on inducing a neutralizing antibody response. Thus, the ideal CMV vaccine should include a combination of multiple antigens inducing a strong cellular and humoral response able to protect against CMV. The aim of this study was to identify and characterize CMV antigens that induce an antibody immune response, and could be used for vaccine design, using serum samples from patients that have developed a protective CMV-specific response after transplantation.

METHODOLOGY

1. Cell culture and Infection

2. Western Blot

3. Protein identification by Liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

4. Gene Amplification and Cloning

5. Transfection into HEK 293-T cells

6. Verification by Western Blot

RESULTS

1. Study population.

29 Serum samples

CMV-specific T-cell immune response

23 patients were negative at baseline and all patients were positive at the time that the post-immune serum sample was collected.

All patients developed high NAb >1/640 one year after transplantation.

Figure 1. Study population. *Nab: Neutralizing antibody

2. Detection of CMV proteins recognized by patient serum samples with high neutralizing antibody titers.

Figure 2. Detection of CMV viral proteins by western blotting. A. Patients that have no neutralizing antibodies at baseline. B. Patients who had low neutralizing antibody titers.

3. Identification of CMV proteins by LC-MS/MS.

Table 1. HCMV proteins identified by LC-MS/MS.

N	%Cov(95)	Peptides(95%)	Database	Gene	Mol. Mass (kDa)	Protein name
1	21.940	6	Accession	UL44	46	DNA polymerase processivity factor
2	9.817	13	P16785	UL48	253	Large tegument protein deneedylase
3	15.690	16	P16729	UL86	153	Major capsid protein
4	23.160	23	P17147	UL57	133	Major DNA-binding protein
5	47.280	49	P09715	IRS1	91	Protein IRS1
6	51.480	48	P16784	UL47	110	Inner tegument protein
7	31.980	35	P09695	TRS1	83	Tegument protein TRS1
8	32.010	22	P06473	UL55	102	Envelope glycoprotein B (gB)
9	66.670	44	P06725	UL83	65	65 kDa phosphoprotein (pp65)
10	25.830	19	P16782	UL45	101	Ribonucleoside-diphosphate reductase large subunit-like protein
11	32.250	21	P16727	UL84	65	Protein UL84
12	27.590	13	P19893	UL122	62	Viral transcription factor IE2

4. Expression and Detection of CMV viral proteins.

Figure 4. Verification of UL44 protein recognition through protein expression and immune recognition *in vitro*. A: Baseline serum B: Post-immunity serum, of patient 23.

CONCLUSIONS

Using serum of immunized patients is an excellent strategy to identify CMV proteins that are able to stimulate an antibody-mediated immunity and may also be involved in mediating a cellular response. Analysis using these candidates as a vaccine will be further investigated in animal models of immunization.

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